

Spectrophotometric methods for the determination of satranidazole

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Three new, simple and sensitive spectrophotometric methods I, II and III have been developed for the quantitative estimation of satranidazole by first reducing it with zinc granules and hydrochloric acid in ethanol followed by its reaction *in situ* with *p*-methylbenzaldehyde (Method-I) and salicylaldehyde (Method-II) in ethanol to form yellow chromogens with λ_{\max} 390 and 425 nm, which obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range 20–100 and 10–50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. Method-III is based on the reaction of diazotization of the reduced satranidazole and its subsequent coupling with *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride at room temperature to form a pink coloured chromogen exhibiting λ_{\max} at 508 nm which obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range 10–50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. These methods have been found to be applicable for quantitative estimation of satranidazole in bulk drugs and dosage formulations.

Satranidazole¹, 1-methylsulfonyl-3-(1-methyl-5-nitro-2-imidazolyl)-2-imidazolidinone, is one of the large series of nitroimidazoles with a potent antiprotozoal activity². In continuation of our earlier work on the estimation of satranidazole³, we report here three simple and sensitive spectrophotometric methods (I, II and III) for the quantitative estimation of satranidazole after converting it into its reduced form using zinc granules and 4 *N* hydrochloric acid in ethanol at room temperature. The complete conversion of satranidazole to its reduced form was confirmed by the disappearance of absorption peak at 315 nm in UV spectrum which is a characteristic peak of satranidazole in ethanol⁴.

Methods I and II developed are based on the reaction of reduced satranidazole (2) (*in situ*) with *p*-methyl-benzaldehyde and salicylaldehyde (Scheme 1) in acidic conditions in ethanol to form yellow coloured chromogens 3 and 4 with λ_{\max} at 390 and 425 nm, which obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range 20–100 and 10–50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. Method III is based on diazotization of reduced satranidazole with nitrous acid and subsequent coupling with *N*-(1-naphthyl)ethylenediamine dihydrochloride (NED) (Scheme 2) to form a pink coloured chromogen 6 with λ_{\max} at 508 nm and obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range 10–50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Results and discussion

The optical characteristics such as absorption maxima, Beer's law limits, molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are presented in Table 1. The regression analysis using the method of least squares was made for the slope (*b*), intercept

(*a*) and correlation coefficient (*r*) obtained from different concentrations and the percent relative standard deviation and percent range of error (0.05 level confidence limits) calculated from eight measurements, 3/4th of the amount of upper Beer's law limits in each method are summarised in Table 1.

Scheme 1

Optimum conditions :

The optimum concentration for the estimation of satranidazole was established by varying one parameter at a time and keeping the other fixed and observing the effect on the absorbance of the coloured species and the conditions were incorporated in the procedure. The effect of

Table 1. Optical characteristics and precision

	Method-I	Method-II	Method-III
λ_{\max} (nm)	390	425	508
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	20–100	10–50	10–50
Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	1.47×10^3	3.18×10^3	0.98×10^3
<i>Sandell's sensitivity</i>			
($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ –0.001 absorbance unit)	0.051	0.061	0.047
Regression equation ($y = a + bc$)*			
Slope (b)	3.70×10^{-2}	2.11×10^{-2}	6.12×10^{-2}
Intercept (a)	0.04×10^{-2}	0.03×10^{-2}	0.04×10^{-2}
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9996	0.9995	0.9998
% RSD	1.211	1.023	1.003
Range of errors**			
Confidence limits with 0.05 level	± 1.36	± 1.25	± 0.93

*Y is the absorbance and C is the concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$. ** For eight measurements.

reagent was studied by varying the reagent concentration from 0.5–1.5% in method I, 0.2–1.0% in method II and 0.05–0.20% in method III and the optimum concentrations were fixed at 1% (1 ml) in method I, 0.5% (1 ml) in method II and 0.1% (1 ml) in method III. The Beer's law limits were obtained by varying the drug concentrations from 20 to 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in method I and 10–50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in methods II and III, by keeping the reagent concentration fixed.

Interference studies :

The interference study showed that the common excipients and additives such as lactose, starch, gelatin and magnesium stearate that are usually present in tablet dosages did not interfere at their regularly added levels upto 50, 40, 20, 8 and 4 mg, respectively, as confirmed by recovery studies.

Sample analysis :

The proposed methods (I, II and III) were applied for the assay of satranidazole in pharmaceutical preparations

(T_1 and T_2) and the results were compared with the reported method⁴. The amounts obtained were 297.92, 298.22, 299.15 and 299.51 mg for sample-1 (T_1) and 298.12, 298.45, 299.06 and 300.30 mg for sample-2 (T_2) for 300 mg marketed tablets by proposed method I, method II, method III and UV method respectively. The percentage recovery values are 99.12 ± 0.5 , 99.32 ± 0.2 and 99.17 ± 0.6 for sample-1 (T_1) and 98.71 ± 0.3 , 99.14 ± 0.08 and 99.34 ± 0.2 for sample-2 (T_2) for method I, method II, and method III which are averages of eight measurements respectively.

In conclusion the proposed methods are simple, sensitive, accurate and can be used for the routine determination of satranidazole in bulk as well as in its pharmaceutical preparations.

Experimental

A Systronics 119 spectrophotometer with 1 cm matched quartz cells was used. All chemicals (Loba Chem) were purified. Satranidazole samples in bulk and in tablet formulations (Alkem Laboratories Ltd., Mumbai) were used.

Satranidazole (1), pure or formulation, 100 mg was accurately weighed, dissolved in alcohol (20 ml) and treated with 4 N HCl (10 ml) and zinc granules (0.75 g) with stirring. After 1 h at room temperature, it was filtered and the residue was washed with ethanol (3×10 ml) and the total volume was made upto 100 ml with ethanol. The final concentration of reduced satranidazole (2) was made to 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

Methods I and II :

To each of the fresh aliquot (1–5 ml) of reduced

satranidazole (2) (1 ml = 200 μg in method-I and 1 ml = 100 μg in method-II), 1% alcoholic *p*-methylbenzaldehyde (1 ml) in method-I and 0.5% alcoholic salicylaldehyde (1 ml) in method-II was added and heated at 60–70° for 20 min. After cooling, the volume was brought upto 10 ml with ethanol and the absorbance of the yellow coloured species (3) in method-I and (4) in method-II were measured at 390 nm and 425 nm respectively against respective reagent blanks. These coloured species were stable for 2 h in method-I and more than 12 h in method-II respectively. These colours were stable upto 80° and at alkaline pH, colour starts fading in both the methods I and II. The amount of satranidazole was computed from calibration curves (Scheme 1).

Method III :

To each aliquot (1–5 ml) of reduced satranidazole (2) (1 ml = 100 μg), conc. HCl (3 drops) and 1% sodium nitrite (1 ml) were added and set aside for 15 min at room temperature. An aqueous solution of ammonium sulfamate (1%; 2 ml) and aqueous solution of NED (0.1%; 1 ml) were then added to each flask at 3 min time interval and diluted to 10 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of pink coloured species (6) was measured at 508 nm against reagent blank after 30 min and before 24 h. The amount of satranidazole was computed from calibration curve. Colour started fading slightly after 24 h and also at alkaline pH (Scheme 2).

The results of the above methods were compared with the reported UV spectrophotometric method⁴. In UV method, solution of satranidazole (1) in alcohol either pure or formulation (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) was prepared. Aliquots of satranidazole (1) ranging from 0.2–1 ml (1 ml = 100 μg) were transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. The volume was made upto the mark with alcohol and the absorbance of the solutions was measured at 315 nm against solvent blank. The amount of satranidazole (1) was computed from calibration curve.

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